

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DRUGS USED FOR THE TREATMENT OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES

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Abstract

Periodontal disease is one of the biggest problems in dentistry. In the treatment of chronic generalized periodontitis of mild to moderate severity, various antibacterial and anti-inflammatory drugs are used. The article presents data on the state of local immunity in patients with generalized periodontitis. The results of conservative treatment of periodontitis using the adhesive balm "Asepta" and the phytopreparation "Stomatofit A" and their impact on the immune status of patients are presented.

Keywords: chronic generalized periodontitis, imudon.

The high prevalence of this pathology explains the relevance of finding ways to increase the effectiveness of its treatment. The ability of inflammatory periodontal diseases to participate in the initiation and development of pathology of other organs and systems determines their general medical significance [1, 5]. The main etiopathogenetic factor in the development of inflammatory diseases of marginal periodontium is subgingival microflora [1, 5]. Modern standards for the treatment of marginal periodontal diseases require an integrated approach, including both etiological (elimination of microbial factors) and pathogenetic effects on the inflammatory process [1,2,7,8]. Dental practice has significant experience in the use of drugs at various stages of the inflammatory process in the treatment of gingivitis and marginal periodontitis [1,9]. At the same time, one of the least studied groups of drugs in this regard are local immunostimulants [3, 4, 6]. In this regard, we conducted a clinical evaluation of the effectiveness of therapeutic measures aimed at eliminating the impact of microbial factors (training and control of personal hygiene, professional hygiene), and a complex method combining the use of traditional methods and immunostimulating therapy using the example of the drug imudon (Solvay, France). Imudon is a polyvalent antigenic complex (lyophilized mixture of dry bacteria), the composition of which corresponds to the pathogens that most often cause pathogenic processes in the oral cavity. Imudon contains the following microorganisms: *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus fermentatum*, *Lactobacillus helveticus*, *Lactobacillus lactis*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Streptococcus sanguis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Corynebacterium pseudodiphtheriticum*, *Fusiformis fusiformis*, *albicans*. By influencing the immune link of the pathological process, imudon has the following therapeutic effects: enhancing

the phagocytic activity of macrophages; increase in lysozyme content in saliva; stimulation and increase in the number of immunocompetent cells responsible for the production of antibodies; an increase in the content of secretory immunoglobulin A (IgA) in saliva; slowing down the oxidative metabolism of polymorphonuclear cells [2, 4]. The control assessment was carried out on the basis of data from outpatient dental health cards registered at the dental department of the 30th city clinic. In the control group, the effectiveness of traditional therapeutic measures aimed at correcting oral hygiene and eliminating the microbial factor of the pathological process was assessed using the OHI-S hygienic index (Green, Vermillion, 1964) and the complex periodontal index KPI (P.A. Leus, 1988), determined before and after treatment measures as part of dispensary observation in 2004. A total of 33 outpatient dental health records were assessed. The experimental group consisted of volunteers from among the patients of the dental department of the 30th city clinic and the Republican Clinical Dental Clinic who applied for marginal periodontal diseases. This group of patients was offered a comprehensive treatment regimen for the disease, combining education and control of personal hygiene, professional hygiene and the use of the drug imudon according to the regimen. Informed consent from the patients was obtained. The study involved 28 people aged 19 to 73 years, of which 12 men and 16 women. At the first visit, the patient's clinical status was assessed during a survey and clinical examination, as well as using the OHI-S hygiene index (Green, Vermillion, 1964), complex periodontal index KPI (P.A. Leus, 1988) and PMA index (Schour, Massler, 1948) modified by Parma. Next, each patient was interviewed about oral hygiene, taught the standard method of brushing teeth and flossing, after which professional oral hygiene was performed using hand and machine

instruments, followed by polishing the teeth and applying fluoride preparations (Fluocal, Septodont). If necessary, professional hygiene was carried out in several visits. The prescription of the drug Imudon was carried out according to the regimen recommended by the manufacturer for the treatment of marginal periodontal pathology: 8 lozenges per day; lasting 10 days. At the end of the first visit, the patient was given 80 tablets of the drug Imudon. The next visits were planned taking into account the necessary therapeutic measures (removal of dental plaque, correction of occlusion, anti-inflammatory therapy). Interim monitoring of the effectiveness of the use of the drug Imudon was carried out on day 5 by repeated determination of the OHI-S, KPI, and PMA indices. The final examination and monitoring of the effectiveness of treatment was carried out on the 10th day, using the same mathematical methods. The average value of the OHI-S hygiene index in the experimental group during the treatment period decreased from 1.3 ± 0.13 to 0.25 ± 0.08 ($p=0.05$), thus the patients' oral hygiene changed from "satisfactory" to "good". In the control group, this indicator changed from 1.2 ± 0.8 to 1.1 ± 0.7 ($p=0.05$), while before and after treatment the values were interpreted as "satisfactory" - "unsatisfactory" hygiene. The value of the complex periodontal index CPI in the experimental group changed from 2.15 ± 0.23 to 0.99 ± 0.27 ($p=0.05$). The indicator of the intensity of inflammation in the tissues of marginal periodontium decreased from the value "moderate" to the value "mild" - "disease risk". In the control group, the value of the complex periodontal index ranged from 1.5 ± 0.9 to 1.7 ± 1.1 ($p=0.05$) before and after treatment, respectively. These indicators are characterized as "moderate" - "mild" forms of inflammation. The most pronounced changes were observed in the PMA index, which was assessed only in the experimental group due to the fact that this index is not mandatory when filling out an outpatient dental health card. At the initial examination, the average value of the PMA index was $38.9\% \pm 4.6$, after the end of complex treatment - $2.8 \pm 1.2\%$ ($p = 0.05$). At the same time, the initial values of the intensity of inflammation in 35.7% of cases were classified as "severe", in 28.6% of cases "moderate" and in 35.7% "mild". After the end of treatment, this indicator had the following form: 82.1% - "moderate", 17.9% - "mild", the indicator "severe" was not recorded.

CONCLUSIONS

The above data show a significant decrease in the intensity of inflammation in the marginal periodontal tissues in the experimental group compared to the control group. This indicates the high therapeutic effect of a complex method of treating acute forms and exacerbations of chronic gingivitis and periodontitis, combining traditional methods of professional hygiene, training and personal hygiene control with the use of a local immunomodulatory drug Imudon. The results obtained allow us to recommend the indicated treatment regimen for marginal periodontal diseases for use in daily therapeutic appointments.

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